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LITERATURE REVIEW

RADIATION CARIES IN PATIENTS WITH HEAD AND NECK CANCER: LITERATURE REVIEW

Cárie de Radiação em Pacientes com Câncer de Cabeça e Pescoço: Revisão da Literatura

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ABSTRACT

Cancer is a heterogeneous group of diseases marked by the uncontrolled proliferation of abnormal cells. Among the most prevalent malignancies in the head and neck region are oral and laryngeal cancers, which often require radiotherapy as part of their treatment. While effective, radiotherapy induces local and systemic side effects, including radiation-induced caries—a rapidly progressing and destructive condition affecting about 30% of head and neck cancer patients. Unlike conventional caries, radiation caries typically begins on smooth surfaces and cemento-enamel junctions, leading to severe crown destruction often without significant pain. It is a multifactorial disease, with primary causes including hyposalivation, decreased salivary pH, and structural damage to enamel and dentin due to radiation-induced free radicals. Contributing factors include trismus, poor oral hygiene, and dietary shifts towards soft, carbohydrate-rich foods. Preventive and therapeutic strategies require a proactive approach from dental professionals, emphasizing rigorous oral hygiene, daily fluoride rinses, artificial saliva, and interim restorations with fluoride-releasing materials such as glass ionomer cements. Definitive restorations using composite resins may be compromised by changes in oral tissues post-radiotherapy. A multidisciplinary team—including dentists, nutritionists, and oncologists—plays a crucial role throughout the cancer care process. Early diagnosis and management of radiation caries are essential to preserve dental structures and ensure the patient's quality of life. This literature review aimed to explore the prevalence, pathophysiology, clinical features, prevention, and management of radiation caries in patients undergoing radiotherapy for head and neck cancers, highlighting the importance of comprehensive dental care in oncologic settings.

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RESUMO

O câncer é um conjunto heterogêneo de doenças caracterizado pela proliferação descontrolada de células anormais, sendo o câncer oral e o de laringe duas das neoplasias mais comuns na região de cabeça e pescoço. A radioterapia, tratamento frequentemente utilizado, causa efeitos colaterais locais e sistêmicos, especialmente devido aos danos às células saudáveis ao redor da área irradiada. Um dos principais efeitos adversos é a cárie por radiação — uma condição agressiva e de rápida progressão que afeta aproximadamente 30% dos pacientes submetidos à radioterapia em cabeça e pescoço. Diferente da cárie convencional, a cárie por radiação frequentemente se desenvolve nas superfícies lisas e junções cimento-esmalte, com destruição severa da coroa, mesmo sem dor significativa. Essa condição é multifatorial, tendo como principais causas a hipossalivação, alteração do pH salivar e fragilidade estrutural dos tecidos dentários devido à ação dos radicais livres. Fatores como trismo, alteração na dieta e dificuldade na higiene oral agravam o quadro clínico. A abordagem preventiva e terapêutica exige atenção especial por parte do cirurgião-dentista, com ênfase na higiene bucal, uso de soluções fluoretadas, saliva artificial e materiais restauradores provisórios como os cimentos de ionômero de vidro. O trabalho multidisciplinar envolvendo dentistas, nutricionistas e oncologistas é fundamental desde o início do tratamento oncológico. Este estudo de revisão buscou identificar, por meio de literatura científica, as principais características, mecanismos fisiopatológicos, formas de prevenção e tratamento da cárie por radiação. A detecção precoce e o manejo adequado são essenciais para preservar a estrutura dentária e melhorar a qualidade de vida dos pacientes oncológicos.

Palavras chave: Radioterapia, Cárie Dentária, Neoplasias de Cabeça e Pescoço

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a heterogeneous group of more than 100 diseases characterized by the uncontrolled proliferation of abnormal cells, with the potential to invade adjacent tissues and spread to distant organs through metastasis. These malignant cells exhibit autonomous growth, a high rate of division, and loss of normal cellular control mechanisms, leading to the formation of tumors that impair the structure and function of affected tissues (HANAHAH, 2022; HANAHAH; WEINBERG, 2011).

Oral cancer, also referred to as cancer of the lip and oral cavity, is a malignant tumor that affects the lips and various structures of the mouth, including the gums, buccal mucosa, hard palate, lateral borders of the tongue, and the floor of the mouth. The disease is more prevalent in men over 40 years of age and ranks among the most common malignancies of the head and neck region. According to recent estimates by the Brazilian National Cancer Institute (INCA), approximately 15,100 new cases are expected annually in Brazil between 2023 and 2025, with 10,900 occurring in men and 4,200 in women, with the highest incidence in the Southeast region (DE OLIVEIRA SANTOS; DE LIMA; MARTINS; OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2023; INCA, 2022).

Laryngeal cancer is a malignant neoplasm that predominantly affects men over 40 years of age and ranks among the most common tumors in the head and neck region. According to estimates from the Brazilian National Cancer Institute (INCA) for the 2023–2025 period, approximately 7,650 new cases are expected

annually in Brazil, with 6,470 in men and 1,180 in women. The highest incidence is concentrated in the Southeast and South regions of the country (INCA, 2022).

Radiotherapy is one of the main modalities used in cancer treatment, relying on the application of ionizing radiation to destroy or inhibit the proliferation of tumor cells. However, it is a non-selective therapeutic approach that can also damage healthy cells located in the peritumoral region and along the path of radiation, leading to both local and systemic adverse effects (BASKAR; LEE; YEO; YEOH, 2012; SALAZAR; VICTORINO; PARANHOS; RICCI *et al.*, 2008).

The ionizing radiation used in radiotherapy primarily exerts its effects through direct damage to cellular DNA, leading to cell death or loss of reproductive capacity. These cytotoxic effects are most pronounced during cell division, particularly during mitosis, when DNA is more exposed and susceptible to damage. Consequently, cells with high mitotic activity are more sensitive to radiation, which accounts for the effectiveness of radiotherapy in tissues with high cellular turnover (HALL; GIACCIA, 2018; JHAM; FREIRE, 2006).

Among the main complications resulting from radiotherapy in the head and neck region are oral mucositis, candidiasis, dysgeusia, osteoradionecrosis, soft tissue necrosis, xerostomia, hyposalivation, and radiation-related caries. These clinical manifestations significantly impair the patient's quality of life and may hinder both the continuation of cancer therapy and the functional rehabilitation of the oral cavity (EPSTEIN; GÜNERI; BARASCH, 2014; JHAM; FREIRE, 2006).

Radiotherapy can significantly impair the buffering capacity of saliva, leading to a decrease in salivary pH from approximately 7 to around 5. This acidic environment creates a critical pH condition that favors enamel demineralization, while natural remineralization processes become ineffective (SALAZAR; VICTORINO; PARANHOS; RICCI *et al.*, 2008). In this context, the main preventive approach against radiation-related caries involves strict oral hygiene management, including regular professional prophylaxis and continuous patient education on home oral care practices (JENSEN, S. B.; PEDERSEN, A. M. L.; VISSINK, A.; ANDERSEN, E. *et al.*, 2010; KIELBASSA; HINKELBEIN; HELLWIG; MEYER-LUCKEL, 2006).

The dental surgeon must provide continuous care to the patient, enhancing oral hygiene through regular prophylaxis and the use of provisional restorative materials, such as glass ionomer cements, which release fluoride and help prevent caries. Although composite resins are the materials of choice for definitive restorations, their polymerization and adhesion are directly impaired by alterations caused by enzyme denaturation and the presence of free radicals generated during radiotherapy (SIRIPAMITDUL; SIVAVONG; OSATHANON; PIANMEE *et al.*, 2023).

The literature shows that managing oncological patients, particularly those affected by radiation-related caries, presents significant challenges. Therefore, clinical planning must be conducted with utmost caution, taking into full account the patient's oral and systemic health status. Furthermore, the coordinated involvement of a multidisciplinary team from the beginning of cancer treatment until clinical discharge is essential to ensure comprehensive and continuous care (EPSTEIN; GÜNERI; BARASCH, 2014; MENDONÇA; GONÇALVES; LIMA; HONORATO *et al.*, 2020).

The objective of this study was to conduct a literature review on the occurrence of dental caries in patients receiving radiotherapy for head and neck cancers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comprehensive literature search was conducted across major databases to identify relevant studies. We evaluated articles published in both Portuguese and English. Studies for which full-text access was not available were excluded. No restrictions were applied regarding the publication date of the articles. The search was performed using descriptors such as "Radiation caries," "Tooth demineralization," "Dental caries," and "Radiation."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Radiation caries in head and neck cancer (HNC) patients develops rapidly and aggressively after radiotherapy, affecting about 30% of them (PALMIER; MIGLIORATI; PRADO-RIBEIRO; DE OLIVEIRA *et al.*, 2020). It presents uniquely, often on smooth tooth surfaces and cusp tips, primarily along the cemento-enamel junction, causing severe crown destruction near the gingival margin. If untreated early, it can lead to crown amputation. Some patients experience less dental pain despite severe damage, possibly due to reduced pulp vascularity caused by radiation-induced fibrosis. Managing radiation caries requires careful treatment planning, favoring advanced adhesive techniques and minimally invasive restorative methods, which are particularly beneficial for patients with limited mouth opening or sensitivity post-radiotherapy (ABED, 2023).

Radiation caries is an indirect consequence of radiotherapy, a primary modality of oncologic treatment. Similar to conventional dental caries, it is a complex, multifactorial, and destructive disease. One of the main etiological factors is hyposalivation, which causes even teeth not directly exposed to radiation to be susceptible to this pathology (FILHO; FREITAS; PINTO; PEIXOTO *et al.*, 2017; JENSEN, S.; PEDERSEN, A.; VISSINK, A.; ANDERSEN, E. *et al.*, 2010).

Radiation caries clinically presents as a rapidly progressing and aggressive condition, with a high potential to affect all dental surfaces. Moreover, it is often painless, which contributes to a poorer prognosis in patients lacking regular dental follow-up, as the lesions may advance faster and involve the teeth in a shorter time compared to conventional caries (TOLENTINO; CENTURION; FERREIRA; SOUZA *et al.*, 2011) (VISSINK; JANSMA; SPIJKERVET; BURLAGE *et al.*, 2003).

Radiation caries lesions commonly begin on the cervical and/or buccal surfaces, exhibiting rapid progression. Early stages are characterized by increased surface friability, evidenced by enamel wear. Microscopically, radiation caries shares features similar to conventional caries (FILHO; FREITAS; PINTO; PEIXOTO *et al.*, 2017). The anatomical distribution of radiation caries is often related to other patient conditions, such as trismus, which reduces mouth opening and hinders proper hygiene of the cervical tooth areas. It is essential for the healthcare professional to educate the patient regarding expected changes and how these alterations affect oral health (VALADÃO; DE LIMA; GOES; GUEDES, 2019).

The development of conventional dental caries is a time-dependent process influenced by multiple factors. However, in the case of radiation caries, this progression occurs at a significantly faster rate. Research indicates that within as little as three months following the completion of radiotherapy, patients may develop extensive and rapidly progressing carious lesions, leading to severe structural damage to the teeth (VALADÃO; DE LIMA; GOES; GUEDES, 2019).

In addition to impairing salivary flow and composition due to radiation-induced damage to the salivary glands, radiotherapy also alters the structure of enamel and dentin. The physical properties of dentin are significantly affected, primarily through hydrolysis of intracellular water, which results in the release of free radicals. These radicals denature collagen fibers, compromising the mechanical properties of dentin. Consequently, the affected teeth become more fragile and prone to structural degradation (BEECH; ROBINSON; PORCEDDU; BATSTONE, 2014; PINNA; MILIA; USAI; CRIVELLI *et al.*, 2020).

Due to hyposalivation, patients experience a significant reduction in both the quantity and quality of saliva, impairing its buffering capacity. Additionally, dietary habits tend to change: the lack of adequate salivary flow makes it difficult to consume fibrous or detergent foods, leading patients to favor soft, carbohydrate-rich foods. This shift further increases the risk of developing radiation-induced dental caries (FILHO; FREITAS; PINTO; PEIXOTO *et al.*, 2017; JENSEN, S. B.; PEDERSEN, A. M. L.; VISSINK, A.; ANDERSEN, E. *et al.*, 2010).

The preservation of dental structures and appropriate management of caries are critical in oncologic patients. One preventive approach includes reducing the intake of acidic foods and beverages. The involvement of a multidisciplinary team is essential, particularly the collaboration between dental

professionals and nutritionists. This cooperation enables the development of dietary strategies aimed at minimizing the consumption of fermentable sugars metabolized by biofilm-associated bacteria. The use of sugar substitutes such as sorbitol or xylitol may be considered a safe and effective alternative (BOWEN; KOO, 2011; GONÇALVES; VALSECKI Júnior; SALVADOR; BERGAMO, 2001).

In addition to improving oral hygiene practices, patients are advised to perform daily rinses with 0.05% sodium fluoride solution and to reduce the intake of cariogenic foods. The use of artificial saliva may be indicated to facilitate the consumption of solid foods and to enhance enamel remineralization (BEECH; ROBINSON; PORCEDDU; BATSTONE, 2014).

Other preventive and therapeutic strategies should also be employed to reduce the development and progression of radiation caries, such as increasing the intake of detergent foods that aid in mechanical plaque control. Cautious use of 0.12% chlorhexidine digluconate and periodic application of 0.5% sodium fluoride are also recommended (ANTUNES, 2020).

CONCLUSION

Radiation caries is an oral condition associated with radiotherapy in cancer patients, characterized by rapid progression and a markedly destructive pattern. Although it shares some structural features with conventional dental caries, its clinical presentation is more aggressive and diffuse. In this context, the role of the dental surgeon is critical for early diagnosis and the implementation of effective therapeutic strategies aimed at preserving tooth structure and improving the patient's quality of life.

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